

SOIL O-LIVE

SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY
OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

D7.16

Project website

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Deliverable 7.16 Project website

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Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
Antonio J. Manzaneda	UJA	Author/reviewer
Iván Sánchez	UJA	Reviewer

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the Deliverable 7.16 “Project website” and it aims to introduce the structure of **Soil O-live website** (<https://soilolive.eu>), developed with WordPress.

This deliverable is led by UJA (University of Jaén), as part of WP7. This official project website will be used by the Consortium throughout Project duration to share communication and dissemination activities and maximize their impact.

To ensure a unified Soil O-live identity across platforms, the project has a visual identity set consisting of the project logo, colors and templates. This is expected to guarantee that the image of the project is easily identified by stakeholders.

Currently, several sections are available to share project general information on “Work-packages”, project “experimental sites”, and “news” related to project activities and presence in press media. The final goal is to engage as many stakeholders as possible, keeping them updated. New sections as “Results” and “Events” are being created now and will be online soon.

1. Website presentation and structure

The official website of the Soil O-live project is hosted at the address “<https://soilolive.eu>”.

The layout of the website is highly user-friendly. The front page (Figure 1) is a dynamic series of olives related images where the titles of the different sections are displayed. Enumeration of the partners and corresponding logos are at the bottom of the front page.

Figure 1. Front page of Soil O-live website

The footer of the website (Figure 2) is designed to highlight the source of Soil O-live funding, that is to say European Union under Horizon Europe Program, specifying also the Grant Agreement Number, the Privacy and Cookies Policies, and social media interactive icons.

Figure 2. Footer of Soil O-live website

The number of sections will grow as the project advances. Currently, in the home page the following sections and subsections are organized in the main drop-down menu as follows:

- o Work Packages → WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP6 + Diagnosis
- o Our orchards → Spain, Italy, Portugal, Greece, Morocco + Orchards images
- o News
- o Contact Us

2. Maintenance and updates

The maintenance of the website will be carried out by UJA with the occasional collaboration of specialist freelance informaticians. *HERMES Comunicación* will be in charge to upload materials on the website.

The “News” section (and soon also the “Events” section) is conceived as a very dynamic part of the website as it is going to grow as project timeline advances. It is regularly updated about project news and recent developments.

News sections will be added to the website menu (already planned “Results” and “Events”) as the projects advances.

3. Website traffic monitoring & analytics

The progress of the website will be monitored periodically (ideally every 6 months) on the website metrics will be carried out by *HERMES Comunicación*. A specific tool of WordPress will be used to generate analytics and examine main website sections areas of interest.

Looking at the traffic will also be very important to improve, if necessary, the strategy set to communicate the project results and disseminate its achievements.

4. Conclusions

The Soil O-live website (hosted at the URL “<https://soilolive.eu>” and developed with WordPress is expected to play a key role in the success of the project impact. Since this will be the primary entry point for stakeholders looking information in the project or in related areas.

It will consist also in a very important tool for the communication & dissemination of the project activities. Some updates and improvements are planned for the website during the project lifetime.